

SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE FORMATION OF THE IMAGE OF ROLE RELATIONSHIPS IN SURKHANDARYA FAMILIES

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the socio-psychological features of the formation of ideas about role relationships in families. The role of the family in the process of socialization of the individual, the mechanisms of role acquisition, identification and social learning mechanisms are scientifically covered. In particular, the transformation of family roles in modern society and its impact on the consciousness of young people are considered.

Nowadays, the family, as the main social institution of society, is of great importance in the formation of personality. The first social experience of each person is formed precisely in the family and in this process is formed on the basis of role relationships. Modern socio-psychological research shows that the future social behavior of a person largely depends on the system of roles mastered in childhood. For this reason, the study of perceptions of role relationships in the family is currently one of the most urgent scientific problems. Social roles in families have a great influence on the spiritual and psychological development of the individual. Each member of the family has a specific role, and these roles are formed, changed, and determined by the situation in the family. The division of roles in the family between father, mother, children, and other members is associated with psychological factors, and each member of the family develops in this role in his own way.

Roles in the family can change depending on the economic, social, cultural, and spiritual status of the family, but from the point of view of psychoanalysis, each member determines his own psychological development path due to the role assigned to him. In particular, these roles are of great importance in interpersonal relationships and the self-awareness of the individual. The issue of the distribution of roles in families in society (including the division of duties, tasks, and responsibilities between spouses, parents, and children) has been studied by many foreign and domestic scientists in the fields of sociology, psychology, family psychology, and ethnopsychology. Currently, the ideas about the family in the families of the Surkhandarya region are being formed in a combination of national and traditional values and modern worldviews.

In every family, marriage is taken seriously, divorce is not welcomed. Anxiety and problems are resolved through patience and the intervention of close relatives. Therefore, the ideas about the

importance of mutual understanding and spiritual compatibility are growing among young people. Unfortunately, nowadays there is a critical view of forced or only customary marriages. This causes conflicts in the distribution and fulfillment of mutual roles in families. The means of its influence are also increasing. [1.87 p]. We can observe the Internet, migration, information flow and other influences. We rely on the scientific views of well-known scientists on this topic, and they are as follows.

Professor G.B. Shoumarov's textbook "Family Psychology" interprets the ideas about family life as follows: "One of the pre-marital factors that decisively affects the strength of the family is the ideas of young people about their own family life. How close they are to reality is the main guarantee of the strength of this family. Unfortunately, our young people's ideas about family life are not always, and in most cases, radically different from reality. Therefore, in preparing young people for family life, it is not appropriate to show family life and marital relations only one-sidedly and only from the good side. It is better to show it as fully as possible, with its ups and downs, its sweetness and bitterness, its joys and sorrows, its dark nights and bright days. Only then can a more adequate idea of family life be formed in our young people." [5,125 p] Indeed, the formation of family role relationships in each society is determined by the roles, traditions, customs, and culture of family members. For example, it is common in many societies to see the father as the provider and the mother as the nurturer.

The perfect fulfillment of these roles, of course, depends on the social environment and upbringing in the family, the relationship between parents, love, respect, and the level of responsibility that the child will fulfill in the future. The character, interests, traditions, and psychological characteristics of each family member also have an impact on how the roles are divided. Therefore, roles are not always the same in all families. Roles in families are not strictly defined, but rather they change positively or negatively over time. But it is also necessary to know this fact, that is, roles can be divided based on mutual agreement, if roles, tasks, and duties are reconsidered. As long as roles are not clearly defined or not correctly distributed, of course, conflicts and conflicts can flare up in this family. For example, failure to share responsibilities, mismatch of expectations in roles, etc. are obvious examples of this. The famous scientist VVKarimova considers the family to be the most important link in society. The norms of behavior and actions that are the result of the emotions experienced in the family environment include: sobriety, orderliness, freedom, sincerity, justice, aspiration, thrift, loyalty, trust, honesty, etc. One of the foundations of the child's experience is the social character that is formed in him under the influence of the parental family. That is, mutual trust, self-esteem, self-concept are qualities that are formed in the child's mind under the influence of his parents, brothers, sisters, and brothers.

[3,72-73 p]. A child learns to live in peace and harmony by observing and imitating their communication throughout his life, and by observing his brothers and sisters, he learns how to behave in complex situations of interaction in society and understands the meaning of life. The distribution of roles in the family is as follows: the father is the leader and financial provider, the mother is the emotional supporter and educator, and the child is the learner and developer. However, according to him, these roles are not fixed, but change over time. [2.98 p].

The formation of ideas about role relationships in Surkhandarya families is a complex socio-psychological situation, which is shaped by national and traditional values, customs, traditional methods of upbringing, and modern social changes. The results of the study show that although the distribution of roles in the family is often based on traditional views, today new ideas about gender equality and personal development are gradually taking shape. The upbringing of children by parents, the atmosphere of mutual respect and cooperation in families appear as a necessary factor in the stability of ideas about role relationships. Especially important in the psyche of the growing younger generation is the adaptation of family roles and the formation of tendencies for mutual responsibility. [5,140-141 p].

In conclusion, in order to further improve the perceptions of role relationships in Surkhandarya families, it is necessary to coordinate family education with modern approaches, strengthen spiritual and educational work, and develop cooperation with family and social institutions. This will serve the formation of healthy, stable, independent, youthful, and harmonious family relationships in the long term.

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